

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

QUALITY, RISK, INNOVATION AND EXPLOITATION MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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Table of Content

List of Figures.....	4
Abbreviations	4
Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Quality Assurance	6
2.1 Meetings.....	6
2.2 Data storage and platforms for collaboration.....	7
2.3 Internal Review Process	8
3 Risk mitigation and management	10
3.1 Risk Identification	10
3.2 Risk Assessment	10
3.3 Risk Mitigation.....	12
3.4 Iterative Risk Management	12
4 Innovation and Exploitation Management Strategy.....	12
5 Conclusion.....	13
6 Bibliography	14
7 Annex	15
Annex 1: Power Point Presentation Template	15
Annex 2: Internal Review Checklist	17
Annex 3: List of Risks according to the GA	19
Annex 4: Work Package Risk Log Template.....	22

List of Figures

Figure 1: FIRELOGUE internal review process	9
Figure 2: Risk likelihood and magnitude (Hopkin 2018, p.22)	11
Figure 3: Firelogue's impact and likelihood matrix.....	11
Figure 4: Presentation Template 1st Slide	15
Figure 5: Presentation Template Content Slide.....	15
Figure 6: Presentation Template Final Slide	16

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
FhG	Fraunhofer Institute for Technological Trend Analysis INT
GA	Grant Agreement
IA	Innovation Action
PC	Project coordinator
WFRM	Wildfire risk management
WG	Working group
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

Good quality, risk, innovation and exploitation management are elementary for the effective and efficient management of the Firelogue project and the impactful utilisation of its results. The roles and responsibilities for each partner have been agreed upon in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement which will serve as the basis for the work conducted for the coming years.

Regular meetings on all Firelogue levels help ensure the effective flow of information, hold partners accountable and allow for the successful completion of the work conducted. Firelogue as a project promotes the dialogue within the Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) community, the same sentiment should thus also apply within the Consortium.

Risk monitoring and management is necessary to avoid potential harm to the project's goals. All partners are called upon to report any potential risks they may see to the Project Coordinator regularly and work on implementing effective mitigation strategies. An initial list of project risks that have been identified during the creation of Firelogue will serve as a first step. They will be updated with each periodic report.

Innovation and exploitation of the Firelogue outcomes will ensure that the project partner's efforts and ideals will be widely known within the community and beyond and will sustain long after Firelogue has ended as a project. At the same time, knowledge and expertise on innovation and exploitation management will be provided to the projects that Firelogue support, i.e. FIRE-RES, DRYADS, SILVANUS and FirEUrisk.

1 Introduction

The central objective of Deliverable 7.1 is to outline core strategies and procedures regarding FIRELOGUE's approach to quality and risk management as well as innovation and exploitation management, as outlined in the Description of the Action (DoA). It specifies roles and responsibilities of all partners involved in achieving the goals of this project.

This deliverable should function as a guide to all partners regarding quality assurance and risk mitigation. Therefore, all partners have been consulted on these procedures and are encouraged to consult this document at any point of the project. Especially the internal review process and the overview of review-responsibilities should be kept in mind and regularly consulted, as there might be dynamic adjustments over time.

Innovation and Exploitation strategies have been developed in a rather generic manner. Since Firelogue is a Coordination and Support Action facilitating the implementation of the Green Deal Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) Innovation Actions and FireURisk, the development of own products is not in the focus. However, the concrete results will be continuously monitored and certain aspects such as the concept on considering Just Transition aspects in WFRM (D4.1) carry great potential for being applied more broadly.

2 Quality Assurance

All partners involved in Firelogue are contributing to the high quality of the project's outputs. This Section articulates the procedures and processes Firelogue partners will undertake in order to ensure such quality, including meetings, data storage, and collaboration platforms.

2.1 Meetings

Regularly scheduled meetings throughout the project's lifetime are necessary and vital not only for productivity but also for well executed quality management. The purpose of the regular meetings mentioned below is to give all partners the opportunity to raise and discuss important issues in their relevant contexts and to inform everyone involved of the project's current progress. They offer the opportunity to collectively find solutions to problems that might arise or on how to identify and mitigate potential risks (more on risk management in Section 3 below) early and efficiently. Together with the meetings' minutes (see below), regular meetings ensure the flow of information between all Firelogue partners.

Fraunhofer INT (FhG) as the project coordinator (PC), will be responsible for organising regular consortium meetings, at least four times a year, and regular Work Packages leader meetings at least once a month. In addition, the thematic Working Groups (WGs) have to be established in year one and hence respective meetings with the WG leaders and thematic strand leaders are also organised at least once a month. For the time being, WP leader and consortium meetings have both been scheduled on a monthly basis, with the option to increase or decrease their frequency as the project progresses over the years, which will be decided upon by the members of the relevant groups. In case of urgent matters, partners have the opportunity to ask for additional meetings, which will be organized by the PC.

WP leaders are responsible to organise their own work package meetings, at least once per month during the WP's lifetime and task leaders are to organise any additional meetings with their respective

partners as needed. Here, too, the frequency can be increased if necessary (e.g. if urgent issues need to be discussed) which will be decided within the respective work packages.

Working group leaders will be responsible for organizing their meeting schedule within their group, in coordination with the project coordinator in case any external stakeholders should be involved.

For each WP leader and consortium meeting, comprehensive minutes will be provided via email (and stored in the Firelogue Teams working space) after each meeting and a record of the meeting will also be kept on accompanying Miro online whiteboards that are accessible through the project's internal Microsoft Teams Channel. WP leaders and task leaders are responsible for their respective meetings and need to decide within their group how a record is to be kept (e.g. detailed minutes, Miro board, etc.).

It is the purpose of any regularly scheduled meeting to ensure that all partners involved receive all necessary information regarding the project's progress. Especially, regular WP meetings are useful to assess the current progress and quality of any ongoing or upcoming work, as well as to mitigate and identify any issues. Monthly WP leader meetings are necessary to discuss progress and arising risks of each WP in the context of the whole project and to identify any issues that span across WPs. Consortium meetings not only bring all partners together on a regular basis, but also provide them with a clear picture of the project's progress. All partners have the opportunity to flag any major potential risk that are threatening the entire project and need to be discussed in the consortium.

2.2 Data storage and platforms for collaboration

Since Firelogue is highly dependent on all partners working together closely and collaborating across organisations, a collaborative working space is vital. Giving partners the space and opportunity to exchange ideas as well as to share their work leads to a higher quality of any output generated by the project. The main collaborative work of the project will be conducted using Microsoft Teams. It is part of the range of Microsoft 365 products and is already widely used among partners. As it has already been proven itself useful during the proposal phase of the project, the collaborative work among partners will continue on this platform. Separate channels have been set up for each WP within the Firelogue team and further channels can also be added as needed during the project's lifetime.

All collaborative work will be stored in Microsoft Teams. This ensures that every partner has access to the documents and files they need to fulfil their work. Access to the Teams working space is handled by the PC and only upon request (in case new team members join the project or people leave the project). Regardless of their sensitivity, all data collected and/or stored should be handled with great care and digression by all partners.

In case sensitive data is collected, the PC will set up a dedicated space on the Fraunhofer ownCloud, these could include any confidential ideas and developments coming out of Firelogue or storing of personal data, for example when it comes to stakeholder management. In order to ensure the trust between partners, any information will be handled with great care. As part of the ownCloud brand, it "is an open-source file sync, share and content collaboration software that lets teams work on data easily from anywhere, on any device" (ownCloud GmbH 2021a). One very important feature is the guaranteed data security that is provided by company. To ensure adequate protection "ownCloud protects your data using state-of-the-art cryptographic measures in transit, at rest and optionally end- to-end" (ownCloud GmbH 2021b). Access to the platform and the relevant data will be decided upon between the PC and the partners involved. Deliverable 7.4 on Data Management and IPR protection

strategy will establish a more detailed data management plan for Firelogue, both for sensitive and regular data management storage.

2.3 Internal Review Process

The general quality management of Firelogue will be based on the governance structure defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA) (Chapter 6) and the Grant Agreement (GA) (DoA Section 3.2.1). These define the roles and responsibilities of all the project partners, as well as their different roles within the project (i.e. WP leader, Task leader, General Assembly, the Advisory and Ethics Board, and Project Coordinator).

Communication partner EDGE will provide templates in the Firelogue-design for deliverables, presentations and all other forms of output. This will enforce the common brand identity and recognition value of the project. All templates will be made available to partners using the Microsoft Teams channel. Templates provided include:

- Deliverable template
- Template for power point presentations
- Checklist for internal review

Examples of the templates provided will also be included in the Annex (Annex 1: Power Point).

All deliverables will be subject to an internal review process, prior to their submission to the EC, in order to achieve highest scientific quality. Therefore, the responsible author (in general the task leader) will forward the finished deliverable to their assigned review partner(s) one month before the final deadline. Review partners will then have seven days to carefully review the deliverable and return it to the lead authors, together with the filled-out deliverable checklist (see Annex 2). Reviewers have the option to mark the deliverable as either “accepted”, “accepted with minor revisions”, “not accepted, major revision needed”, or “not accepted”. In the first two cases, the lead author has the option to revise the draft or hand it directly to the PC for final review, no later than 10 days before the final deadline. The PC will also review the draft with the same grade-options as before. Once the draft is accepted it will be submitted to the EC by the coordinator. If, at any point, the draft is not accepted the lead author is required to revise the draft according to the suggested revisions. In case of major issues, the reviewer(s), lead author and the PC will set up a dedicated meeting to determine a solution suitable for everyone involved which take the reviewer(s) comments into account.

A more detailed overview over the review process can be found in Figure 1 below.

Ideally, reviewers have not been part of the writing of the deliverable but have some level of expertise or knowledge on the subject. If they have contributed to the draft, partners are asked to pass the draft along within their organisation to a person who has not contributed. Before the submission of D7.1 to the EC, all partners were asked to consult the suggested reviewer-assignment table and flag any problems or inconsistencies they might see.

At all stages of the review process, the reviewers and the lead author will keep the PC in the loop. This way the PC is already informed about current developments and aware of conversations should any issues arise. The PC will also give their final okay on the finished deliverable and is responsible of submitting the finished version to the EC on time.

Figure 1: FIRELOGUE internal review process

3 Risk mitigation and management

All projects are faced with their own unique risks that need to be identified and managed. As a certain level of risk cannot be avoided, regardless of how well the project is managed, there is a need for constantly monitoring possible negative effects and their likelihood of occurrence. Risk can, in this case, be described as any form of unexpected happenings with the potential to damage or enhance the project's goals and objectives (George 2020). The awareness and (early) action to mitigate potential risks and their possible consequences are necessary throughout the project's lifetime. It is, therefore, the task of the project coordinator to actively work on identifying, analysing and managing potential risks.

An initial list of risks has already been established by the consortium and encompasses the most common risks for project management in general, as well as more specific risks to the Firelogue project's goals (Annex 3). Over the course of the project, partners are encouraged to extend this list as they see fit. An updated list will be included in the Firelogue Periodic Reports submitted to the EC. Depending on the risks identified and their assessment, different mitigation strategies will be employed by the PC and project partners to minimize the impact or likelihood of occurrence. The following sections will outline in more detail the tasks and responsibilities of each partner along the different phases of risk management.

3.1 Risk Identification

All project partners are called upon to report any possible risk they may identify in their work. The responsible points of contact are their respective task leader, the work package leader, or ultimately the PC. This also includes the possible risk, as well as any mitigation strategy they have in mind. An emphasis should be placed on early identification, developing plans for addressing them, and reporting as they are crucial to avoiding and mitigating larger harm to the project.

Work package leaders are, in turn, called to register any potential risk reported in a Work Package risk log (Annex 4: Work Package Risk Log Template) so that risks and mitigation strategies can be discussed among WP leaders and the coordinator at the next WP leader meeting.

Due to the large number of external stakeholders involved in Firelogue, their input on potential risks can prove fruitful. It is, therefore, highly encouraged for all partners to also consider potential risks and mitigation strategies that go beyond the internal work of Firelogue and include the collaboration with external stakeholders and the Innovation Actions in particular.

3.2 Risk Assessment

Identified risks will have to be assessed based on their probability of occurrence, their potential impact on the project as well as possible mitigation action to be taken. The assessment will determine how urgently an action needs to be taken and what possible mitigation actions are available to minimize the risk's harm to the project.

Risks are therefore scored according to (1) their likelihood of occurrence (high – medium – low) and (2) their possible impact on the project (high – medium – low). Both categories are scored on a scale

Figure 2: Risk likelihood and magnitude (Hopkin 2018, p.22)

from 1 to 3 (low=1; high=3). The risk's overall score is determined by multiplying the two category- scores (likelihood-score x impact-score = risk level), as detailed in Hopkin's (2018) version of a risk matrix see Figure 2). Assessed risks scoring between 1 and 2 are highlighted in green. These risks need to be accepted as given, their impact and likelihood is small enough not to become a threat to the project. Nevertheless, they need to be monitored constantly, in case their impact or likelihood scores change over the course of the project's lifetime. Risk scores between 3 and 4 are highlighted in yellow. They, too, need to be continuously monitored and mitigation strategies should be sketched, with the aim to limit or avoid their occurrence. Immediate action might not be required. Lastly, risk scores of 6 or higher are located in the red areas (see Figure 2). Due to their possibly high impact and the fact that they are likely to occur, actions need to be taken immediately to eliminate them entirely or to mitigate the effect they have on the project.

Risk likelihood and magnitude matrix			
Impact	3	6	9
	2	4	6
	1	2	3
	Likelihood		
Legend	Low	Medium	High

Figure 3: Firelogue's impact and likelihood matrix

3.3 Risk Mitigation

Identified project risks scoring above 2 points will have to be discussed at the quarterly GA meetings in order to increase awareness and to come up with effective mitigation strategies. The main responsibility lies with the respective WP leader and the PC. Risks that affect more than one work package will be handled by the respective WP leaders together. Risks that have been assessed to pose a major risk to the Firelogue project (i.e., risk scoring greater or equal 6) need to be reported to the EC by the coordinator. The decision whether mitigation measures are deemed as fitting will be up to the respective WP leader(s). Should no consensus be found, the PC will have the final say over the sufficiency of mitigation measures.

Any mitigation measures should address the causes of the identified risks as effectively as possible and reduce both their potential harm, as well as their likelihood of occurrence.

3.4 Iterative Risk Management

The PC will keep a comprehensive list of all project risks identified in the shared working space on the Microsoft Teams channel that will include a description of the risks' probability and their impact. Before each quarterly GA meeting, the list will be updated by the PC so that it can serve as a basis for any discussion during the meeting, especially if any major potential risks have been identified. Possible decisions regarding risk mitigation strategies and measures will be added to the table after the meeting as well.

All partners are encouraged to regularly consult the list to make themselves aware of any possible risks that are relevant to their work and the project and, most importantly, recommended mitigation strategies. The here described process of identifying, assessing and mitigating risks will be an iterative process that will run throughout the project's lifetime. Risks that have previously been assessed as low likelihood of occurrence and/or low impact, might have a higher impact and a higher likelihood of occurrence in a year or two. It is, thus, necessary to not only add new project risks to the list but also to constantly review and reassess already identified risks and to amend the list as necessary.

4 Innovation and Exploitation Management Strategy

As outlined in the DoA, innovation and exploitation management are an integral process of the Firelogue project to ensure an impactful uptake of the project's outputs.

The European Commission defines an innovation as "the use of new ideas, products or methods where they have not been used before" (Eurostat 2012). In an earlier Green Paper on Innovation, a distinction was made between the process of innovation, meaning the process from an idea to use, and the final result of said process, e.g. a finished product, practice or service (European Commission 1995). While Firelogue as a Coordination and Support Action does not foresee any direct development of innovations, its main focus will be on developing support for innovations (including processes and measures) developed by the IAs and FirEUrisk. Through providing a forum for dialogue among WFRM stakeholders, Firelogue hopes to foster an environment for new innovation processes to take place, which might eventually support the development of innovative products, practices or services within the Innovation Actions (IAs). In order to ensure an effective and adaptive strategy, bi-annual reviews will be conducted, examining project activities and outputs, which includes their innovation and exploitation potential. Overall, the three IAs and FirEUrisk will be supported in their exploitation efforts by all Firelogue partners, by the co-design of exploitation or the implementation of measures such as the Technology Market Place (TechMall) and the Firelogue Stakeholder platform (WP6). All these

efforts will closely cooperate with the EC services such as the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre.

At the same time, some of the Firelogue outputs can be regarded as innovations as well. For example, the conceptual development of Just Transition approached to managing wildfire risk (D4.1), the Firelogue platform and tech mall could be regarded as outputs that are worth exploring their innovation and exploitation potential. A focus will also be put on the exploitation of the work conducted in the Working Groups.

In order to establish a mechanism for continuously reviewing own developments and activities outside the consortium, dialogue and exchange between project partners and external stakeholders, such as the IAs, is vital. Activities outside of the project consortium that will be observed include technological development, development of procedures as well as development of standards and regulations.

The exploitation of the project results will be measured in relation to the utilisation and impact of outcomes during the project and after its conclusion. Overall, there are two levels relevant for assessing Firelogue's impact. On the one hand this concerns the support of the IAs and FirEURisk in their innovation and exploitation activities and use of own results (such as the abovementioned framework or tech mall). At the same time, WP3 will develop and assess the impact of WFRM innovations and measures – especially in regards to the impact goals as set by the EC (D3.1). Firelogue will do so in close collaboration with the Green Deal projects and FirEURisk and their experts.

5 Conclusion

The Deliverable aims primarily at the project partners as a guidance and reference document for their future work within the project. It outlines the quality assurance process, all deliverables will have to go through before being submitted to the EC. Additionally, it clarifies each partner's role and responsibility regarding their part in proactively avoiding severe project risks and in handling any new and arising issues.

Lastly, it explains the innovation potential of Firelogue and how its results are supposed to be exploited. The best work within a project does no good if it cannot transcend the project's boundaries and is not implemented within the wider thematic community. At the same time, as a Coordination and Support Action, it is of the utmost importance that the Firelogue puts the results of the IAs and FirEURisk in its focus and facilitates their promotion and integration including the translation into policy recommendation for the wider WFRM community.

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7 Annex

Annex 1: Power Point Presentation Template

 THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101036534

Figure 4: Presentation Template 1st Slide

 THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020 RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101036534

Figure 5: Presentation Template Content Slide

THANK YOU

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Figure 6: Presentation Template Final Slide

Annex 2: Internal Review Checklist

Internal reviewers are asked to fill out this review report. In addition, reviewers may provide comments directly in the deliverable draft, using the comment and/or track changes mode (optional). Internal reviewers are asked to return both documents to the deliverable's lead author in time.

Deliverable No. and Title	
Reviewer – organisation	
Reviewer – name	
Date of review	

Overall review result – Please mark ONE option with an « x »	
Accepted, no changes required	
(Minor) revision necessary, repeated review not required	
(Major) revision necessary, repeated review required	
Not acceptable	
Clarity of the content – Please answer each question, specify your answer if needed.	
Are the objectives of the deliverable clear?	
Are the contents consistent with the description in the DoA?	
Does the structure of the deliverable help to convey the main messages?	
Does the deliverable have a consistent logic and clear message?	
Are the arguments made convincing?	
Is it clear how the deliverable supports the overall project objectives?	
Are the inputs and outputs of the deliverable within the project described?	
Is there anything missing?	
Is the level of detail appropriate?	
Does the Executive Summary reflect the main objectives, methodology and results of the deliverable?	
Does the Conclusion properly outline what the results will be used for?	
Further comments (optional)	
Further suggestions for improvement (optional)	

Formalities – Please answer each question, specify your answer if needed.

Is the language and style clear and concise?	
Are tables and figures properly displayed (e.g. size and readability of text)?	
Are sources adequately cited?	
Has the deliverable template been used properly?	
Further suggestions for improvement (optional)	

Only in case a repeated review is required – please fill in after revision:

Review result of the revised deliverable

Have your review comments been properly addressed and implemented? If not, please explain.	
Is another revision required?	

Annex 3: List of Risks according to the GA

Risk number	Description of risk	WP Number	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Likelihood – Impact
1	Withdrawal of a key partner from the consortium	WP7	The coordinator will ensure quality assurance, reporting procedures and communication culture within the consortium to allow the early identification of issues. As the consortium is resourceful enough to re-organise and redistribute most responsibilities, the impact on project outputs of a partner leaving the consortium, or being relieved, will be low. If the loss of a partner cannot be compensated from within the consortium, the consortium can tap into its extensive network and is likely to find an external replacement organisation at short notice.	Low likelihood – Low impact
2	Disruption of communication and collaboration between partners.	WP7	The issues addressed in FIRELOGUE can touch upon sensitive issues for all participating partners, such as internal procedures and responsibilities. Project partners are aware of this. An open and constructive collaboration culture within the project is therefore essential to identify differences in view at an early stage. Much thought will be given to ensure the kick-off meeting fosters mutual trust, a common understanding of the topics and provides consortium members with a chance to align their views and create a common nominator for the project.	Low – Medium
3	WPs need more time than envisaged and deliverables also needed as input for other tasks are delayed	WP7	Due to frequent plenary meetings (2-3 per year) and monthly WP telephone conferences and close collaboration between the coordinator and the WP leads, potential delays will be identified as early as possible to identify concrete mitigation measures. They can encompass extensions, support from other partners, or eventually the adaptation of the work plan or deliverables.	Low – low
4	Ethics and security concerns slow or stop the project	WP7	WP7 will monitor and proactively address ethical and privacy related issues. It will be guiding the consortium to implement data privacy and security procedures, e.g. by supporting the partners in generating user consent forms, which will also be cleared by the Ethics Manager and the Ethics Advisory Board. All ethical concerns that might arise through the involvement of vulnerable groups will be flagged at the beginning of the project and during biannual revisions.	Low – low
5	Timing of milestones can create bottlenecks	WP7	Whereas the middle phase is mainly marked by the two workshop cycles, the beginning of the project and the end phase of the project result on many important outputs and milestones. If partners fail to deliver or other risks result in	Medium – high

			delays, the timing of the project can become an issue if not properly managed.	
6	Collaboration with the IAs and wider WFRM community stagnates	WP2, WP6, WP7	FIRELOGUE is dependent on contributions from and collaboration with the IAs funded under this call, but also the wider WFRM community in general. Stagnation would pose a serious problem to the project. All partners will contribute to ongoing communication and networking efforts in order to ensure constant participation in FIRELOGUE activities. We can build on strong networks within the wider WFRM community and will build strong relationships with the IAs to avoid such problems. Finally, continuous assessments of stakeholder needs and the co-creation of dialogue formats should ensure that relevant topics are addressed by FIRELOGUE.	Medium – high
7	Exploitation targets not clear, measurable or achievable in the given time frame	WP6	Clear exploitation goals set early, supported by a concise IPR review; exploitation plan covers both incremental improvements and significant development steps – must be realistic, measurable and achievable.	Low – low
8	Limited outreach due to weak dissemination plan and activities	WP2, WP4, WP6	Different stakeholder networks have been identified in section 1.3.2. Partners will continue to identify stakeholders and relevant events during the project duration. All partners will be engaged in planning awareness raising efforts. Finally, FIRELOGUE will implement and exploit awareness raising, knowledge exchange and peer- learning events. Key impact factors and main communication channels will be determined for different target groups at the beginning of the project.	Low – high
9	Weak media interest due to strong scientific and technology aspects	WP2, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	Due to large end-user involvement and increasing societal impact of wildfires, it is generally expected that the media interest should be high. Particular effort will be made to disseminate results to the public. Nevertheless, FIRELOGUE remains complex and technical. All partners will hence make effort to explain outputs in easy-to-understand-language. In addition, information to be disseminated will be tailored to dedicated communities.	Low – low
10	Dissemination constraints due to classified information	WP6, WP7	FIRELOGUE does not foresee the use of classified information.	Low – low

11	Limited communication with target groups due to language barrier.	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	Translation of guidance and training materials to local language. Translation of dissemination materials into the language of the target group to the extent possible.	Medium – low
12	COVID-19 pandemic results in sustained restrictions	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	Restrictions on social interaction will have several key impacts on the project. Project meetings can be held via tele- or videoconference, drawing on experiences by project partners in how to facilitate such events in the best way possible under these circumstances. Working group meetings can to some degree be held virtually as well, using an array of online meeting and participative tools, such as polling tools or digital whiteboards (such as Miro). Should physical meetings be possible, a detailed hygienic concept will be in place to ensure the safety of all involved. The consortium has partners with vast experience in methodology, co-creation and interactive / participative methods to ensure co-creation can still take place in the best way possible.	Short term: High – Medium/ longer term: Low – low

Annex 4: Work Package Risk Log Template

Risk number	Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	Likelihood – Impact score
1			
2			
3			
4			

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